

ISic3568

I.Sicily inscription 3568

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Cava d'Ispica

Provenance

hypogeum, contrada Finocchiara, Cava d'Ispica

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Cava Ispica, contrada Finocchiara, hypogeum

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337415

1. [— —]Φ²crack in the rock² NE[— —]M[— —]N
2. X.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645639

PHI 337415

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 54.0929.1

Rizzone, V.G., Sammito, A.M. 2005. Nuovi documenti epigrafici dal circondario di Modica. In Rizzo, F.P.(eds.), *Da abitato in abitato. In itinere fra le più antiche testimonianze cristiane degli Iblei*. Rome. pp. 45-62. At 51

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